

Germplasm improvement

Genetics

Improved lines with wide compatibility (WC) gene of Moroberekan

D. Senadhira, R. M. Herrera, and J. P. Roxas, IRRI

We previously reported that the WC gene of Moroberekan is very effective but that this upland variety might not be the best WC source for use in lowland rice breeding programs. Moroberekan performs poorly in anaerobic soil. Uneven tillering and flowering and abnormal tillers are common. Desirable recombinants are rare when Moroberekan is used as a bridge variety in indica × japonica crosses.

We made a series of crosses with Moroberekan to develop improved lines adapted to flooded soil conditions and possessing Moroberekan's WC gene. Crosses were advanced under irrigated conditions at IRRI. We used modified bulk method for five generations; selection was based on normal growth

Spikelet fertility of new WC lines, their parents, and F₁ with japonica (Akihikari) and indica (IR36) testers. IRRI, 1993 DS.

Variety/cross	Spikelet fertility (%)
IR61614-3B-3-1-1	92.3
IR61614-3B-6-2-3	94.4
IR61614-3B-7-3-3	96.6
IR61614-3B-12-3-3	93.9
IR61614-3B-19-3-2	92.2
IR36	95.2
IR32429-47-3-2-2	94.9
Akihikari	95.4
Moroberekan	95.9
Akihikari/IR61614-3B-3-1-1 (F ₁)	87.2
Akihikari/IR61614-3B-6-2-3 (F ₁)	81.1
Akihikari/IR61614-3B-7-3-3 (F ₁)	85.4
Akihikari/IR61614-3B-12-3-3 (F ₁)	87.7
Akihikari/IR61614-3B-19-3-2 (F ₁)	84.1
IR36/IR61614-3B-3-1-1 (F ₁)	89.5
IR36/IR61614-3B-6-2-3 (F ₁)	84.6
IR36/IR61614-3B-7-3-3 (F ₁)	91.5
IR36/IR61614-3B-12-3-3 (F ₁)	94.7
IR36/IR61614-3B-19-3-2 (F ₁)	90.8

and plant type characteristics. Pedigree selection was used thereafter. In the F₇ generation, agronomically uniform lines from two crosses were tested for the presence of the WC gene. The lines were hybridized with an indica (IR36) and a japonica (Akihikari); F₁ fertility was examined.

All lines of the cross IR61315 (Moroberekan/IR66) showed normal fertility (>85%) with IR36 but were partially fertile (<40%) with Akihikari. Five lines derived from the cross

IR61614 (IR32429-47-3-2-2*/Moroberekan) showed normal fertility with both japonica and indica testers. They were tested again in 1993 dry season (DS) and the presence of the WC gene in IR61614 lines was confirmed (see table).

Unlike Moroberekan, the new lines are adapted to anaerobic soil conditions and possess high-yielding plant type characteristics. They mature in 125 d and are highly resistant to blast. Seeds of these lines are available from IRRI. ■

Breeding methods

A self-sustaining system for hybrid rice seed production

S. S. Virmani, J. Manalo, and R. Toledo, IRRI

One of the disadvantages of hybrid rice technology is that cultivators must secure new seeds every season. To produce pure hybrid rice seed, fields must be

isolated from adjoining ricefields flowering at the same time. This condition is difficult to achieve in many rice-growing areas. We propose a system in which hybrid rice growers

Proposed field layout of a self-sustaining system for hybrid rice seed production.

